

THE ROLE OF CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATIONS IN DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS MAJORING IN OIL AND GAS

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the consideration of the role of cross-cultural communications in developing professional competence of students majoring in oil and gas. The author analyzes how cross-cultural awareness helps develop professional and terminological competences of future specialists.*

Keywords: *professional competence, oil and gas sphere, cross-cultural communications, engineering university.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola neft va gaz talabalarining kasbiy kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirishda madaniyatlararo muloqotning rolini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Muallif madaniyatlararo muloqot omillari b'lajak mutaxassislarining kasbiy va terminologik malakalarini rivojlantirishga qanday hissa qo'shishini tahlil qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *professional kompetentsiya, neft va gaz sektori, madaniyatlararo aloqalar, texnik universitet.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена изучению роли межкультурной коммуникации в развитии профессиональной компетентности студентов нефтегазового профиля. Автор анализирует, как факторы межкультурной коммуникации способствует развитию профессиональных и терминологических компетенций будущих специалистов.*

Ключевые слова: *профессиональная компетентность, нефтегазовая сфера, межкультурные коммуникации, технический вуз.*

As the world becomes increasingly interdependent, so does the need for a global language. The worldwide movement towards a more integrated world economy has brought major changes to the international business system. Globalization has resulted in the substantial growth of international trade and economic opportunities. With businesses becoming more and more global, communication is not only important, but imperative.

One of the biggest challenges, which is experienced by companies in the process of expansion, is linguistic diversity, which can stifle growth if not addressed accordingly. Successful companies continuously seek ways to differentiate themselves from competitors in order to gain a competitive advantage- and in the aggressive business world- multinational corporations need employees who are capable of communicating and collaborating effectively. Poor communication practices can make an adverse effect on an organization's bottom line; therefore, businesses need to focus on adopting a global language strategy to facilitate internal and external communication with partners, customers, and employees.

As the business world becomes increasingly global, the need for effective cross cultural communication is essential. Cross cultural communication in business plays a vital role in building international customers, employee relations and business partnerships. Cross cultural communication in business requires effort, technique and the addressing of different hurdles that commonly prevent communication from being effective. English has rapidly become the most widely used language in the world of trade and commerce over the past few decades. As a result, having an excellent knowledge of English for business has become vital for success in any

employee’s career. No more so than in that of international students seeking better career prospects in an English speaking country.

The spread of the English language can be traced back to the days of the colonial expansion and has fast become the default language in all official forms of communication in most countries around the world. In today’s business oriented world, English is widely used as the major medium of communication for both small business concerns and large corporate entities alike. As the Lingua Franca in almost all of the developing nations all over the world, English is the preferred language in the business community as many business partners nowadays do not speak the same native language.

It can cross international borders and transcend language compatibility barriers that have made English the most sought after language in today’s corporate world. The proficiency of the language has also made it a vital part of [success in the highly competitive corporate world](#). Many reputed organizations around the world rely on English as a means of communication in everything from emails to corporate documentation to even popular and well-read business resources both in print and over electronic media. English is being used as the official language in over 70 countries. Fluency in English, both written and spoken plays a critical role in many aspects of corporate life from securing employment to communicating with clientele and achieving cohesive business partnerships all over the world.

English has now become a global language for business all over the world to such an extent that it is the standard official language in certain industries such as the shipping and airline industries. It has resulted in the knowledge of English being a near-mandatory requirement for critical jobs such as airline pilots and naval officers, etc. Apart from having an impressive command of spoken English today’s competitive corporate culture demands an equally impressive command of written English as well. It is mainly because almost all forms of business communication such as emails, presentations, sales and marketing and even corporate legal documentation are now carried out in English.

Intercultural, or crosscultural business communication is one of the most critical factors contributing to business growth and success in the global world. The ability of companies to acquire intercultural competence can either make or break their chances of success in an increasingly competitive, international business arena. As a result, many companies and organizations are wisely investing in cultural awareness training for their leaders and employees in order to tap into some huge potential international markets.

Each culture has a different set of values, business ethics, languages, behavior, expected etiquette and expression. Not knowing the differences in the country that the company is doing business in can lead to communication barriers that prohibit the messages from being effective. Conveying meaning in business communication is of the utmost importance. One has to start with some idea of what the audience or market is required to understand, and this has to be narrowed down to one specific message. Under current conditions no one has the time or patience to figure out a well-intended but obscure purpose. This is particularly true when one is trying to persuade someone towards a line of reasoning, as in an advertisement, sales pitch or job interview. When the sole intent is to market the business, make sure you know the difference between advertising and public relations. Advertising involves paying to promote your business through various media. Public relations don’t cost anything and refers to anything that conveys a positive image for a business. Networking can aid a company’s public relations effort in talking to potential customers, council members and others vital to getting the word out. While networking may cost a business

executive a lunch here or there, it's main expense is your time and In the new socio-economic conditions development of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan receives a high status, since it is precisely this that will contribute to the transition to an information society and the formation of the government development priorities. The policy of openness of Uzbekistan, active entry into the world market, and expansion of international cooperation in all areas increase the need for knowledge of foreign languages. Proficiency in foreign languages and the ability to use them in professional activities and during the research have become an urgent requirement of the time. As it has been noted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, “The time has come to create a new system of teaching foreign languages in our country, which will become a solid foundation for the future”, which has necessitated the need to search for new approaches to teaching foreign languages, creating new academic and teaching materials that meet modern requirements, as well as constant improving the qualifications of foreign language teachers. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 №PR-5117 “On measures to raise the activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level” identified a number of priority tasks for all educational institutions aimed at improving the quality of education and the population’s interest in learning foreign languages.

It should be noted that significance of learning foreign languages has always been on the focus of attention of the government of our republic. “It is high time to create a new system of teaching foreign languages in our country, which will become a solid foundation for the future. We must be competitive in a rapidly changing world. We need to strengthen the study of foreign languages in order to strengthen the foundations of the Third Renaissance”, the President noted at a video conference meeting held on May 6, 2021.

On November 14, 2023, the President Assistant Saida Mirziyoyeva held a meeting with foreign educators to draw up a roadmap for cooperation, emphasizing that “If we want to raise a smart, decent, self-confident generation, we need two things - love for our native language and solid knowledge of foreign languages. Languages are the key to peace, access to global information and the thirst for new knowledge”.

It is obvious that modern realities dictate the conditions according to which a university graduate, in order to be in demand on the labor market, must not only have professional knowledge, but also know foreign languages, in particular, the specialty-based terminology.

Currently the Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University) named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent provides education for specialists for the oil and gas industry in 11 subject areas and specialties.

These are 5-year academic curricula on the “Geological Exploration Technology” subject area with specializations “Digital Geoengineering”, “Geophysical Methods of Well Exploration”, as well as “Oil and gas engineering and technology” subject area with specialties “Development and operation of oil and gas fields”, “Technology for onshore and offshore drilling oil and gas wells”.

Bachelor course: “Oil and gas business” subject area with academic profiles “Drilling of oil and gas wells”, “Operation and maintenance of gas production facilities, gas condensate and underground storage facilities”, “Operation and maintenance of oil production facilities”, “Operation and maintenance of transport and storage facilities for oil, gas and refined products”, “Construction and repair of gas and oil pipelines and gas and oil storage facilities”, subject area

“Economics” with academic profile “Economy and sustainable energy development projects”, subject area “Management” with academic profile “Business management in energy sector”.

In a view of considerations specified above, the fact that at oil and gas industry enterprises, along with the state language, Russian and English are widely used, as well as the presence of representative offices of foreign companies and joint ventures in our republic, this determines the relevance of English language proficiency for oil and gas industry specialists.

Proficiency in professional terminology, as well as good communication skills in English will provide future specialists of oil and gas business with the following benefits:

- ability to read and understand in English instructions on the use of equipment and technologies and design documentation, which is developed based on technical English;
- ability to use geological software systems to build virtual 3D models of oil and gas fields with an interface in English, used by almost all oil and gas companies;
- opportunity to study foreign experience in the use of modern oil and gas production technologies, know the capabilities of new equipment, get acquainted with innovation-based developments and advanced achievements of science and technology by reading specialized literature, professional magazines in English;
- skills to perform professional communication with foreign experts and partners in English;
- have the prospect of career growth, since in the oil and gas industry, in light of the use of the latest innovation-based developments in modern digitalization conditions, the demand for highly qualified engineers who speak English and are able to use it is increasing.

Proficiency in professional terminology, as well as good communication skills in English will provide future specialists in economics and management focus areas with the following benefits:

- ability to read English-language business periodicals in the original and introduce advanced foreign experience at the enterprise;
- ability to work in the original language with financial plan documentation (agreements, contracts, payment documents), which is maintained in English all over the world;
- be aware of the latest events in the world of economics and finance, since most large exchanges and trading platforms where securities, metals, energy resources and other assets are sold or purchased also operate in a foreign language;
- get employment in a foreign company;
- conduct business correspondence with foreign partners.

In conclusion it should be noted that there are new and emerging changes going on in the field of communications resulting from changing demographics of the communities in which the business must operate. Cross cultural communication in business plays a vital role in successfully establishing the product or service in a different area of the globe. When the communication is effective, the product or service is appropriately tailored to the cultural norms and expectations resulting in the use or purchase of the product. Ineffective communication cross culturally can offend, confuse or send a misunderstood message which could lead to broken relations with investors or employees.

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